

Event metadata

Event title	Getting started with proteomics
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	07/06/2023
Time of event	1pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Proteomics aims to identify and quantify all the proteins and peptides within a sample. Mass-spectrometry is the most common tool for proteomics and the wide array of methods, techniques and specialised approaches available have made it a popular method for probing cells, tissue and organisms in response to various stimuli or diseases.</p> <p>Each proteomics method has unique experimental design considerations and optimum workflows for data analysis meaning that there is no one-size-fits all solution. The variety of approaches available provides flexibility but can be bewildering and a barrier to getting started.</p> <p>This webinar sets you up with the foundational knowledge of what to look out for when designing and understanding proteomics experiments. It outlines what you can and can't do with proteomics, the type of data to expect as well as common data analysis approaches and quality control steps.</p> <p>This webinar was developed in collaboration with the Australian Core Facilities and Australian Proteomics Communities.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/proteomics-webinar
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Proteomics http://edamontology.org/topic_0121 Mass spectrometry data http://edamontology.org/data_2536

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Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians who are embarking on proteomics experiments as part of their research.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this webinar you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outline the steps in a proteomics experiment ● List sources of bias and variation in proteomics experiments ● Describe QC plots for proteomics data ● List sources of support and training on proteomics
Speakers	<p>Dr Luke Carroll, Technology Manager - Mass Spectrometry, Australian Proteome Analysis Facility, Macquarie University</p> <p>Associate Professor Matt Padula, Director - Proteomics, Lipidomics and Metabolomics Core Facility, University of Technology Sydney</p> <p>Dr Johan Gustafsson, Bioinformatics Engagement Officer, Australian BioCommons</p>
Related material	None